

A PRACTICAL METHODOLOGY FOR THE FATIGUE TESTING OF HYBRID JOINTS

A. Pierpoint¹, M. Hill¹ & C. Bagni¹

This work presents a practical methodology for the fatigue testing of hybrid joints – a type of load-transferring joint where structural adhesive is used in conjunction with mechanical fasteners. The method was successfully used by HBK's Advanced Materials Characterisation and Testing (AMCT) facility in the UK. Bespoke specimen geometries were designed to be both representative of in-service joint configurations, whilst permitting the calculation of all the various mathematical parameters used in the fatigue models. Various grades of automotive metals were tested. Defects in the joints can have an effect on the amount of scatter present in the Load-Life data. Identifying these issues early, through a thorough pre-test inspection of the specimens, can help when analysing and understanding the test data. The correlation of images recorded during testing with drops in stiffness of the joint can be used to define alternative failure criteria to specimen separation. This can allow the selection of a more representative failure criterion and can sometimes aid in reducing the amount of scatter in the Load-Life data when compared with using specimen separation as the failure criterion. The testing methodology presented in this paper enables the generation of high quality Load-Life data sets as required to obtain good quality fatigue parameters generated through reverse engineering using Finite Element results.

Keywords: Fatigue Testing, Hybrid Joints, Adhesive, Self-Piercing Rivets (SPR), Resistance Spot Welds (RSW)

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a transition towards developing more sustainable and energy-efficient methods of transportation. This is particularly apparent in the automotive industry which is undergoing a significant technological shift in order to reduce the environmental impact. As a result, hybrid joints are becoming more popular thanks to the weight reduction benefits brought by the adhesive (reduced weight of the adhesive compared to traditional mechanical fasteners, and reduced number of required mechanical fasteners) and their ability to join dissimilar materials allowing for further material and design optimisation. A hybrid joint is a combination of two or more joining techniques, commonly an adhesive and a mechanical fastener such as self-piercing rivets (SPR) or resistance spot welds (RSW), which are used to produce a single joint with improved properties when compared with the individual joining techniques. An increase in mechanical properties is clearly seen

¹ Hottinger Brüel & Kjær UK Ltd, Advanced Manufacturing Park Technology Centre, Brunel Way, Rotherham, South Yorkshire, S60 5WG, United Kingdom

in works by Sadowski et al. [1] and Moroni and Pirondi. [2] who found that combining a mechanical fastener with an adhesive layer resulted in an increase in tensile strength of around 2.2 times and 1.7 times, for RSWs and SPRs respectively. Furthermore, both types of hybrid joints showed an increase in stiffness, when compared to joints with only mechanical fasteners. Another benefit of hybrid joining techniques is that the adhesive layer distributes the stress evenly across the joint, whereas in joints using only mechanical fasteners, high stress concentrations can be found in the areas around the fasteners.

Literature reviews carried out by Maggiore et al. [3] and Abdel Wahab [4], highlighted that hybrid joints generally show better tensile performance compared to joints using only mechanical fasteners. On the other hand, they show worse tensile performance compared to purely adhesive joints. Moroni [5] found that this is because the maximum load of a hybrid joint is dictated by the adhesive layer and the reduction in maximum load of hybrid joints compared to adhesive only joints is caused by the reduction in adhesively bonded area due to the presence of the mechanical fasteners. Moroni also found that the fatigue life of hybrid joints is increased when compared to adhesive or mechanical fastener only joints as the mechanical fasteners can aid in decreasing the rate of crack propagation in the adhesive. This is shown by the change in compliance of the hybrid joints remaining constant for an increased number of cycles in comparison to adhesive or mechanical fastener only specimens. However, this is not true for high-load, low-cycle fatigue tests as the static properties of the joint have a stronger influence, meaning that adhesive only specimens can perform better compared to hybrid joint specimens. Additionally, Moroni found that the sudden increase in compliance was a result of complete failure in the adhesive. Beyond this, the load was sustained by the mechanical fasteners only. This is also seen in the work by Wu et al. [6], where the failure of hybrid joint specimens was split into two stages: a first stage where cracks initiate and propagate in the adhesive layer, followed by a second stage where cracks initiate and propagate around the mechanical fasteners.

It is important that the specimens to be tested are representative of the manufacturing method and quality of real-world production components; otherwise, the data obtained from fatigue testing will not be representative and may be non-conservative. One example, as presented by Al-Samhan and Darwish [7], is the amount and shape of adhesive spew. In particular, filleted bond lines had increased performance compared to square edge bond lines. The overall bonded area can also have an impact on the performance of hybrid joints as the strength of the joint is proportional to the size of the bonded area. Melander et al. [8] found that a large difference can be observed in the tensile strength between joints with sufficient bonded area and joints with a reduced bonded area. Furthermore, Shahani and Pourhosseini [9] found that an increase of the adhesive thickness can also have a positive effect on the fatigue performance and can, in some cases, change the failure location from the adhesive to the substrate. Each type of defect can cause a different issue and this can also be impacted by the type of adhesive and mechanical fasteners used in the joint as well as the specimen geometry which is being tested. For example, brittle adhesives are more likely to be affected by the quality at the ends of the joints, as found by Wang et al. [10], whereas more ductile adhesives are more likely to be affected by the overall quality of the bonded area, as shown by Schonhorn et al. [11].

The fatigue characterisation of hybrid joints is imperative for their successful implementation in the design of more environmentally friendly vehicles. Lap shear and coach peel are the most common test specimen geometries as they are relatively easy to test and they should offer a ‘best and worst’ case scenario, since adhesives tend to perform best when subject to shear loading and worst when subject to peel loading, as shown by Pirondi and Moroni [12]. This paper aims to detail the

methodology for the testing of hybrid joints which has been successfully developed and implemented at HBK's Advanced Materials Characterisation & Testing (AMCT) facility in Rotherham, UK. The successful implementation of this methodology has resulted in the generation of multiple high quality datasets.

METHODOLOGY

Specimen design and pre-test specimen inspection

As described earlier, lap shear and coach peel are the most common specimen geometries used when testing hybrid joints. However, other specimen geometries can be tested if considered more appropriate. The lap shear (FIGURE 1a) specimen geometry is designed to generate predominantly shear stress in the adhesive with some amount of peel stress. The coach peel (FIGURE 1b) specimen geometry is designed to generate predominantly peel stress in the adhesive. Manufacturing consideration must be made when designing test specimens to ensure they are as representative as possible of the joints in the real production components. As a result, the same materials and thicknesses (for both substrates and adhesive) and manufacturing processes used in production must be adopted. Furthermore, the mechanical fasteners must have the same spacing as in the real components and they should (ideally) be spaced far enough from each other and from the edges of the specimens to avoid interaction and edge effects. For this reason, the overall width of the specimens must be adapted to accommodate all these factors. The total length of the specimens may also vary and this is mainly governed by the required gripping length and free length of the specimen. The required gripping length is dictated by the type of grips and fixtures used in the tests and the anticipated maximum uniaxial load required, whilst the free length of the specimen is mainly dictated by the target specimen behaviour, and the type and amount of load experienced by the joint. The substrates used to manufacture the specimens should be of the same material(s) and have the same thickness(es) used in production as these can have an impact on the behaviour of the specimens during testing (e.g. thinner or weaker materials will deform by a larger amount than thicker or stronger materials).

FIGURE 1 Specimen geometries for (a) Lap Shear and (b) Coach Peel. All dimensions in mm (not to scale).

Before testing, specimens are inspected for any defects which may cause issues during testing. The types of defects can be grouped into 3 categories: adhesive issues, mechanical fastener issues, and substrate issues. A list of these can be seen in TABLE 1 and some examples of these can be seen in FIGURE 2. It is important to note that not all of the defects in a specimen can be observed during a pre-test inspection as some are only visible after the specimen has separated.

The control mechanisms of the adhesive bondline thickness can be done externally, through the use of tooling and jigs, or internally, through the use of glass beads or wire spacers. Control mechanisms for adhesive spew shape is done by wiping the adhesive to give the required angle or fillet radius. FIGURE 3 shows an example of a coach peel specimen with different adhesive spew amounts and FIGURE 4 shows an example of a lap shear specimen with different fillet angles. Full fillets which cover the top substrate were not present in this project so have not been included in the figure.

TABLE 1 Descriptions and likely causes of defects which can be found in hybrid joint specimens (adhesive issues – 1.X, mechanical fastener issues – 2.X, and substrate issues – 3.X).

ID	Defect	Appearance	Likely cause
1.1	Lack of adhesive	The adhesive does not cover all of the required areas	Not enough adhesive used, poor adhesive distribution or poor wet out
1.2	Macro-voids and micro-voids	Macro-voids or micro-voids present in the adhesive	Gasses trapped in the adhesive during application or curing
1.3	Disbonding of the adhesive to the substrate	Contamination causing lack of bonding of the adhesive to the substrate	Improper preparation and cleaning of the substrate surface
1.4	Incorrect adhesive bond thickness	The adhesive thickness is incorrect or is inconsistent	No or poor control mechanisms for bondline thickness control
1.5	Incorrectly cured adhesive	Adhesive is soft or discoloured	Incorrect curing parameters or no curing at all
1.6	Adhesive spew	Excess of adhesive outside of the bonded area	Incorrect amount of adhesive used, no or poor control mechanisms for spew control
2.1	Misalignment of the RSW or SPR	RSW or SPR are not aligned to the centre of the specimen	No use of a JIG or extraction is not straight
2.2	Incorrect amount of fusion in the RSW	The size of the RSW is not correct	Incorrect welding parameters or electrode used
3.1	Misalignment of the substrate sheets	Substrate sheets are not parallel or are offset	No use of a JIG or extraction is not straight
3.2	Defects on the substrate sheets	Marks, scratches or defects on the substrate sheets	Marks from machining processes or handling

FIGURE 2 Examples of defects seen in hybrid joint specimens.

FIGURE 3 Examples of spew size in coach peel specimens

FIGURE 4 Examples of fillet shapes in lap shear specimens

Test setup

Fatigue tests are performed under constant-amplitude, sinusoidal tension-tension load control, to avoid buckling of the specimens. The load levels of each test should be selected to avoid plastic behaviour of the parent material (this generally corresponds to fatigue lives of $1E4$ cycles to separation and above). The test frequency is varied appropriately, according to the load level and test configuration and to ensure there is no self-heating during testing. The tests are typically performed at ambient laboratory conditions unless the joint within the production part is to be subjected to significant non-ambient conditions during service. An example setup for testing hybrid joints can be seen in FIGURE 5.

FIGURE 5 An example of a test rig setup for testing (a) lap shear and (b) coach peel hybrid joints with the deflectometer and camera highlighted in blue and red, respectively.

The top and bottom grips are designed to be modular, allowing for different substrate thicknesses and widths to be used with minimal modification required. Alternatively, conventional wedge grips can be used. During initial setup, alignment bars are used to ensure perfect alignment of the top and bottom grips within the load train. The recessed area in the centre of the grips has the same width as the standard specimen geometry and enables easy alignment of the specimen. A 60 Nm torque is applied to each of the 6 bolts to hold the specimen in place. When testing the lap shear specimen geometry, spacers which have the same thickness of the substrate are used to account for the offset between the two plates and ensure that the load is applied through the centre of the specimen.

The load applied to a specimen is measured using a load cell of suitable capacity with the force being applied by a hydraulic actuator. The hydraulic actuator has a displacement transducer which is used to measure displacement. An additional displacement transducer, such as a deflectometer, is used to record the displacement of the specimen throughout the testing. The deflectometer is low range but high accuracy, allowing for more accurate displacement data to be recorded. The values of all three transducers are recorded at a rate of 100 points per cycle, every 10 cycles. Additionally, the maximum and minimum values are recorded for each cycle.

A camera with a built-in light source is used for taking images of the specimen throughout testing and is operated using a custom Python™ script. A time interval of 30 seconds is used as this gives a good balance between the number of cycles between images and the number of images taken per test. The recordings are used to allow post-test visual detection of crack appearance in the adhesive and understanding of how the crack propagated.

Tensile tests can be performed on specimens in order to gain an understanding of the strength and behaviour of the joint as this will help during initial fatigue testing. The test setup in terms of

specimen geometry and test rig fixturing should be identical to the fatigue tests. The test should be operated in displacement control with load and displacement being recorded throughout the test. Plotting these values as a load-displacement curve will help understand the behaviour of the joint. FIGURE 6 shows an example of a load-displacement curve obtained from a tensile test performed on an adhesive + RSW lap shear specimen. Initially, the specimen has a linear elastic behaviour (red region). At the end of the linear elastic region, cracks begin to form in the adhesive and propagate throughout until failure of the adhesive occurs (green region). Beyond this, the RSWs carry the full load applied to the specimen and the substrate around the RSWs starts to fail, resulting in nugget pull out (purple region). It has been found that initial fatigue tests with a maximum load of around 75% of total load in the linear region on the tensile plot have typically resulted in lives around $1E4$ cycles to separation.

FIGURE 6 Example Load-Displacement curve of a lap shear adhesive + RSW specimen. Red region – linear elastic response, green region – failure of the adhesive and purple region - failure of the RSW.

Fatigue analysis

The fatigue analysis is performed by considering the number of cycles corresponding to one or more of the following failure criteria:

1. Specimen separation

Specimen separation is achieved when the specimen is in two or more pieces. However, in order to protect the test equipment, the test rig is configured to stop when the displacement transducer reaches a certain value, which can leave ductile materials physically intact but with very significant cracks visible. A value of 20mm maximum displacement has been found to be suitable and is used as the displacement limit to stop a test. At this point, the specimen is considered separated for fatigue purposes and the number of cycles is recorded.

2. Stiffness drop

The specimen is considered to have failed when the stiffness has decreased by a given value and the number of cycles is recorded. As a crack propagates within a specimen, the stiffness value of the specimen begins to drop. The stiffness of a specimen is calculated using the following equation:

$$K(N) = \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta u(N)} \quad (1)$$

where ΔF and Δu are the load range and the displacement range, respectively and are defined by the following equations:

$$\Delta F = F_{max} - F_{min} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta u(N) = u_{max}(N) - u_{min}(N) \quad (3)$$

During testing, the specimens are cycled at a constant load amplitude and therefore ΔF remains constant. As a crack(s) begins to propagate, Δu increases, resulting in K decreasing. As the values described above can change depending on multiple factors including the specimen composition and geometries, and load amplitudes during testing, it is good practice to use a normalised stiffness defined using the following equation:

$$K_n(N) = \frac{K(N)}{K(N_0)} \cdot 100[\%] \quad (4)$$

where N_0 is a given number of cycles when the following conditions are met:

- The cyclic load has reached the target maximum and minimum amplitudes and both amplitudes are stable.
- The value of the normalisation stiffness $K(N_0)$ must not be decreasing due to the propagating fatigue crack. This is not always possible; for example, the stiffness of coach-peel specimens, due to their geometry, could decrease from the beginning of the test. In this case, N_0 is chosen as close as possible to the beginning of the test but ensuring that the first condition is met.

3. Crack appearance

Images obtained throughout the tests are reviewed to identify the time at which the crack can first be observed. The number of cycles corresponding to this time are calculated. Due to the recording interval of 30 seconds this is an approximation of first crack appearance, however, this level of accuracy is considered acceptable for the purpose of correlation with the stiffness data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of adhesive + SPR coach peel tests are used as a case study. It is noted that not all the defect types listed in TABLE 1 were present in these specimens. For confidentiality reasons, the data presented in this paper has been manipulated and/or anonymised, but the overall trend of the data is representative.

Failure criteria

1. Specimen separation

Using specimen separation as the failure criterion requires no additional analysis but is non-conservative. The number of cycles to specimen separation (or displacement limit) are recorded and the corresponding datapoints are plotted on the LN graph, shown in FIGURE 7 as red datapoints.

FIGURE 7 LN plot, using log-log scale, for the cycles to separation (red), the cycles to 20% stiffness drop (blue), and the cycles to first visible crack (green) for an adhesive + SPR coach peel hybrid joint specimen.

2. Stiffness drop

Using stiffness drop as the failure criterion requires additional analysis to be performed, but the selected stiffness drop values can be chosen to be representative of the most suitable failure event, meaning the conservatism of the data can be chosen. The analysis required to identify stiffness drops from test data can be automated through a custom script that calculates the stiffness at each cycle and then provide the corresponding cycles to selected stiffness drops. FIGURE 8 shows an example normalised stiffness plot for a coach peel specimen. The number of cycles to a selected stiffness drop for the tested specimens are recorded and the corresponding datapoints are plotted on the LN graph, shown in FIGURE 7 as blue datapoints.

FIGURE 8 Example of a normalised stiffness to cycles curve for a coach peel specimen

3. Crack appearance

Using crack appearance as the failure criterion requires additional analysis of the recordings of the tests to be performed and can be over-conservative as the life of the mechanical fastener still remains. The process to identify crack initiation is also subjective, as it depends on the skills, experience and opinion of the individual performing the activity. Furthermore, it is often a lengthy process. FIGURE 9 shows example images recorded during testing of a coach peel hybrid joint specimen. The number of cycles to crack appearance for the tested specimens are recorded and the corresponding datapoints are plotted on the LN graph, shown in FIGURE 7 as green datapoints.

For illustration purposes, 20% stiffness drop was chosen as the failure criterion. This value of stiffness drop, in most cases, corresponded to a number of cycles close to the number of cycles to crack appearance in the adhesive. Additionally, the normalised stiffness, shown in FIGURE 8, shows that a 20% stiffness drop is approximately equal to half of the fatigue life of the adhesive and therefore, produces reasonably conservative results. Furthermore, from FIGURE 8, it can be observed that after around 40% stiffness drop, the stiffness of the specimen decreases at an increased rate and the difference between the cycles to 40% and 87.5% (complete adhesive failure) stiffness drop is significantly smaller than the difference between the cycles to 20% and 40% stiffness drop.

FIGURE 9 Example of (a) first image during testing and (b) crack appearance in the adhesive (yellow box) during testing of a coach peel hybrid joint specimen. The light in the images is from the camera system.

Correlation between crack appearance and stiffness drops

Reviewing the images taken during the testing means the number of cycles to key failure events such as crack appearance, complete failure of the adhesive and complete failure of the mechanical fasteners can be correlated to certain stiffness drops. For coach peel hybrid joint specimens, a crack appearance can generally be observed between a 20%-40% stiffness drop. Complete failure of the adhesive can generally be observed at stiffness drops greater than 80% (a value of 87.5% stiffness drop was chosen as a representative value across the tests in this case study). Finally, complete failure of the mechanical fasteners occurs towards the end of the test where an accelerated stiffness decrease is observed.

It is recommended to review the recordings of the tests to identify the key failure events such as crack appearance in the adhesive, complete failure of the adhesive, etc. for a number of different tests spread across the life range (e.g. 1 or 2 specimens at around each of 1E4, 1E5 & 1E6 cycles to

separation). This helps to gain a better understanding of the behaviour of the joint and can aid in the selection of the most appropriate stiffness drop to use as failure criterion. Furthermore, using stiffness drop as failure criterion, instead of crack appearance for each single test, can reduce the amount of time required for analysing the data. Additionally, looking at where the failure initiated and how it propagated can help to understand any sources of scatter in the data and identify any specimens that have a failure mode that is out of family.

Data quality and the impact of defects

The resulting LN plot for tests on adhesive + SPR coach peel specimens revealed two datasets emerging: a primary family of datapoints and a secondary family with comparatively improved fatigue performance. FIGURE 10 (generated using the same set of test data used to generate FIGURE 7) shows the LN plot comparing the number of cycles to separation (or displacement limit), the number of cycles to 87.5% stiffness drop (corresponding to adhesive failure), and the number of cycles to crack appearance. The majority of the datapoints belonging to the primary family showed a large difference between the number of cycles to an 87.5% stiffness drop and the number of cycles to crack appearance, whereas, the datapoints belonging to the secondary family showed very little difference and had more consistency in the ratio between the number of cycles to an 87.5% stiffness drop and the number of cycles to crack appearance. A post-test specimen inspection revealed that this was likely due to the amount of spew present in the coach peel joints. In particular, an increased amount of adhesive spew led to an increase in fatigue life when compared with specimens tested at the same or similar maximum load levels. It was also observed that several specimens had macrovoids within the adhesive on the fracture face of the specimens. All but one of these specimens had slightly shorter lives than other specimens tested at similar load levels. Finally, in specimens with both macrovoids in the adhesive and large adhesive spew, it was observed that the negative effect of the former was mitigated by the positive effect of the latter.

FIGURE 10 LN plot, using log-log scale, for the cycles to separation (red), the cycles to 87.5% stiffness drop (yellow), and the cycles to first visible crack (green) for an adhesive + SPR coach peel hybrid joint specimen.

CONCLUSION

This paper details a practical methodology for the fatigue testing of hybrid joints which has been successfully developed and implemented to generate high quality datasets at HBK's AMCT facility in Rotherham, UK. The following conclusions can be made:

- It is important that the specimens produced for testing are representative of the manufacturing methods and quality that is seen in real-world production; otherwise the results obtained from testing may not be representative and could be misleading.
- The amount of scatter present in the LN plots can be affected by defects that are present in the specimens. Therefore, inspecting the specimens, both pre- and post-test, can give valuable insight into the behaviour of each specimen.
- Each type of defect can have a different effect on the fatigue life of the hybrid specimens, with some having more of an impact than others.
- Specimen separation is the easiest failure criteria to identify. However, it is non-conservative.
- Calculating the stiffness of a specimen throughout testing can be automated using a custom script and the stiffness drop selected as the failure criterion can be tailored to the level of conservatism required.
- The detection of first crack appearance is subjective and is strongly dependant on the individual performing the process and can also be time consuming. Furthermore, it can be a lengthy process and may be over-conservative as the life of the mechanical fastener still remains.
- It is recommended to use the recordings of the tests to identify crack appearance in the adhesive, complete failure of the adhesive, etc., but just as a guideline for choosing the most appropriate stiffness drop to use as the failure criterion.
- In the Case Study for adhesive + SPR hybrid joint, specimens with a larger amount of adhesive spew had an increased number of cycles to failure whilst also having a smaller number of cycles between crack appearance and 87.5% stiffness drop (complete adhesive failure) when compared to specimens with a smaller amount of adhesive spew.
- An increase in adhesive spew also seemed to mitigate any negative impact other defects such as lack of adhesive bonding had on the performance of the specimens.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Sadowski, T., Golewski, P., and Kneć, M., *Compos. Struct.*, Vol. 112, 2014, pp. 66-77.
- (2) Moroni, F., and Pirondi, A., *In: da Silva, L., Pirondi, A., Öchsner, A. (eds) Hybrid Adhesive Joints. Adv. Struct. Mater.*, Vol. 6, 2010, pp. 79-108.
- (3) Maggiore, S., Banea, M. D., Stagnaro, P., and Luciano, G. , *Polymers*, Vol. 13, No. 22, 2021, 3961.
- (4) Abdel Wahab, M., *Int. Sch. Res. Notices*, Vol. 2012, 2012, pp. 1-25.
- (5) F. Moroni, *J. Adhes.*, Vol. 95, No. 5-7, 2019, pp. 577-594.
- (6) Wu, G., Li, D., Wei-Jen, L., Yandong, S., Hongtae, K., Yinghong, P., and Xuming, S., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 142, 2021, 105948.
- (7) Al-Samhan, A., and Darwish, S., *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, Vol. 142, No. 3, 2003, pp. 587-598.

- (8) Melander, A., Linder, J., Stensiö, H., Larsson, M., Gustavsson, A., and Björkman, G., *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 22, No. 5, 1999, pp. 421 - 426.
- (9) Shahani, A. R., and Pourhosseini, S. M., *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 42, 2018, pp. 561-571.
- (10) Wang, T. T., Ryan, F. W., and Schonhorn, H., *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, Vol. 16, No. 8, 1972, pp. 1901-1909.
- (11) Schonhorn, H., Ryan, F. W., and Wang, T. T., *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, Vol. 15, No. 5, 1971, pp. 1069-1078.
- (12) Pirondi, A., and Moroni, F., *In: da Silva, L., Pirondi, A., Öchsner, A. (eds) Hybrid Adhesive Joints. Adv. Struct. Mater.*, Vol. 6, 2011, pp. 109-147.